

**THE ROLE OF NGOS IN RURAL EMPOWERMENT: A CASE STUDY OF SKDRDP
KADUR**

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Abstract

Our country is basically a agriculture centered economy and the majority of contribution to the GDP is coming through that one only. Apart from contributing to the welfare of the people, it is the major source of employment for the rural people. Rural people growth has been limited due to the fact that majority of areas don't have basic infrastructure due to which the firms and industries does not choose it as an investment avenues. Though various NGOs have their own effort to uplift the quality of living among the rural people, the work of SKDRDP stands brightly as compared to other NGO programmes. This paper is an attempt to understand the various schemes launched by SKDRDP and to evaluate the awareness of the same on the part of rural people. Various quesitonarries were duly analyzed on the basis of available data before arriving at a conclusion.

Keywords: *Development Programmes, Employment Generation and Rural Empowerment*

Introduction

After the LPG reforms we can see that there has been gradual difference and an unbalanced growth of rural and urban sector. Urban India has been very successful in attracting majority of companies as their favorite investment avenues and hence we can see the change in their quality of life. Same case is not with rural India who have been suffering due to lack of

basic infrastructure facilities and thus lacking the firms to attract as investment avenues. The result is lack of employment generation activities in rural India, which is forcing the rural people Indians to migrate from rural India to urban India. Though the things have been changing with the involvement of NGOs in rural India. Apart from providing them funds, they are providing ample opportunity for the rural people to get employed in their village itself. These schemes are meant to ensure that there is balance growth between the rural and urban sector. The rate of interest charged by these firms is nominal and is a major tool in preventing the people from falling in the traps of rural sahumars. The way of recovery is also phenomenal and no coercive method is used for getting back the money. Various innovative schemes have been enrolled in the village and women's were duly motivated to take up challenging activities and stimulated to come up with shining colours in all areas and same is proving to be very effective. Introduction of MGNREGA Act is a additional benefit and is playing very significant role in reducing the migration of people from rural areas to urban areas. Though the Government has planned certain schemes but the implementation of the same is in high question. The awareness of the people for basic amenities is still a cause of concern due to high level of illiteracy among the rural people. SKDRDP, is a NGO which is working for the cause of the people. Shree Kshetra Dharmasthala Rural Development Programme is a innovative programme, which is meant for the development of the rural people in various spheres of their life. SKDRDP is a service oriented institution who works under Shree Kshetra Dharmasthala Trust. The schemes of this organization are spread for all sections of people and are working from years to provide a effective and efficient life to the rural people. The organizations attempt is not only recognized at national level, but various countries have appreciated the same and various awards and rewards have been presented to the firms due to its enduring effort in global arena.

Review of Literature

Grabe, Shelly (2012) observed that in the wake of globalization women's empowerment, human rights discourse and women's activates within social movements can bring about transformation in structural inequities and provide them with social justice

Data Analysis

The data was analyzed by tabulating the data collected through various questionnaire and were analyzed in later point of time to arrive at an conclusion.

Table 1. Demographic Profile

Particulars	Responses	No of Respondents	Percentage
Age	20 – 25	05	12.5
	25 - 30	09	22.5
	30 - 35	12	30.0
	35 & Above	14	35.0
Total		40	100.00
Educational Status	Illiterate	17	42.5
	Primary	10	25.0
	Middle	09	22.5
	Secondary & Above	04	10.0
Total		40	100.00
Poverty Status	BPL	33	82.5
	APL	17	42.5
Total		40	100.00

Total Family Members	1-3	09	22.5
	3-6	10	25.0
	6-9	13	32.5
	9 & Above	08	20.0
Total		40	100.0
Annual Income of Family	Below 50,000	17	42.5
	50,000 – 1,00,000	13	32.5
	1,00,000 – 1,50,000	06	15.0
	Above 1,50,000	04	10.0
Total		40	100.0

From the table we can observe that majority of the respondents are in between age of 35 & above. This is due to the fact that it at the initial stage of their life, people are not that much interested to follow SKDRDP schemes and in that time the seriousness level is also missing. As far as education level is considered we can see that majority of the respondents are illiterate and due to which there dependence on financial incentive provided by SKDRDP is more and further respondents who are educated couldn't able to find adequate opportunity for job and hence they are dependent on the schemes of the SKDRDP for having an qualitative life. Apart from that the spread of education is also limited in the region, due to lack of basic amenities and it further adds to vows of the normal people. The table further helps to understand that the majority of respondents have limited sources of earnings due to the limited employment opportunity they have in the rural life. Apart from agricultural opportunities the remaining employment opportunities are limited. This due to the fact that various schemes which has been adopted by the government for the upliftment of the rural people is still remaining on the paper only and lots of practical study needs to be conducted by the government for improvement of the people. Mainly in the rural areas the people are in joint family system and hence we can find that the number of dependents is more due to which we can find enhanced family size and the ever

growing expense also extends the burden on the people. The share of the BPL is further more as compared to APL respondents. It is due to fact that the rural people have not too much opportunity for earnings by which they can improve their quality of life. Further we can also find that the majority of the respondents have limited income and it is due to the fact that the majority of earnings which rural people are getting is from agriculture only and it further worsens there problems.

Table 2. Awareness of the Rural Empowerment Schemes of SKDRDP

Awareness of the Rural Empowerment Schemes of SKDRDP	High Level	Moderate Level	Low Level	Total
Women Empowerment Schemes	43	33	24	100
Most Credible mode channelizing Fund	39	33	28	100
Acts as a medium for social and economic integration of rural people	34	39	27	100
Infrastructure Development Programmes	30	36	34	100
Community Development schemes	33	38	29	100
Enivormental protection programmes	35	39	26	100
Technology and market linkage programmes	29	33	38	100
Skill and development and Educational programmes	39	33	28	100
Rural Employment trainaing programmes	37	39	24	100

Programmes. Apart from that we can find that firm now a day's taking regular interest in understanding the rural peoples and it takes its training related programmes to enhance the same. Social security is of very necessitate. Now a day's SKDRDP are actively participating in enhancing the same in the modern era by providing various schemes and developmental programmes. Health is something which now a day's holds paramount of interest and firms are actively engaged in providing quality health programmes through conducting various health related programmes. Financial assistance programmes is provided to the members of the SKDRDP and they are provided with various financial incentives by the same. Apart from that high nutrition value programmes are conducted so as make the members feel happy, as many of the peoples are suffering from malnutrition.

Table 3 – Participation of the communities towards various Schmes of SKDRDP

Programmes	Women	Agriculturist	Rural Entrepreneurs	Labours	Others	Total
Women Empowerment Schemes	23	26	22	20	9	100
Infrastructure Development Programmes	21	23	27	25	4	100
Community Development schmes	19	17	29	24	11	100
Enivornmental protection programmes	21	28	23	22	6	100
Technology and market linkage programmes	22	18	29	26	5	100

a raising concept in every national and international summit. The reason for this hot debate is due to the fact that there has been rapid decline in the growth of the forest and deforestation has been undertaken in a rapid pace. Here we can observe that its agriculturist who are actively participating in the same. Application of the technology is the neccisate of the hour. Technology transformation is growing in every sphere of the life and training programmes are conducted to make understand the recent advancement of the same. In the above table we can find that agriculturist are the major interested parties who implicate the responsibility of applying the technology in agriculture products. Interpersonal skill development of the people is of paramount neccisate and it is due to the fact that majority of the respondents are dealing with the various outsiders and hence the developing of the same is of paramount necessity. Rural employment training programmes are conducted on the regular basis so as to imbibe the necessary skills among its members which ensures their success in the long run and is thus a basis for the enhancing individual efficiency. Various social security schemes are conducted by the SKDRDP so as to ensure long term growth of the society as whole. Here we can see that it is majority of the women's who participate in this type of the programmes. Health awareness and financial assistance programmes are conducted by the SKDRDP so as to ensure that health and financial incentives are reachable to the persons in proper time and proper space.

Findings

1. SKDRDP have played a major and active role in improving the social and economic conditions of individual member in particular and society as whole
2. Financial incentives provided by the SKDRDP are easily available and maintain transparency in the same is given due importance
3. Technological and various skill development activates conducted by the SKDRDP should be very appreciated

Suggestions

1. Infrastructural programmes conducted by SKDRDP are not properly applicated, because it requires huge funding and government agency should be searched for the same.
2. Apart from providing various programmes, educational related programmes needs to be undertaken as still majority of the children are not interested in education

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